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Research Article

IMPROVED LIFE SPAN FOR PATIENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES OVER THE LAST SEVEN AND A HALF DECADES

¹Dr. Umer Shehzad Ahmed, ²Dr Auroosh Sagheer, ¹Dr. Hafiz Aadil Ahmad

¹District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital Sargodha

²Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Aim: To investigate the survival with diabetes in patients treated with insulin from diagnosis.

Methods: We dissected 845 subjects, 55.9% of types, enrolled in "I". We separated the subjects into two groups by age at the end of the study: group A <18 years and group B 18-39.99 years. We used 22-year periods for the year of death: 1946- 1965, 1966-1985 and 1986-2005. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020.

Results: The mean age at diabetes beginning was 31.37 9.05 years, infection span at death 20.98 11.62 years and age at death 53.35 15.38 years. The mean expansion in endurance with diabetes was 19.3 years for bunch A and 13.7 years for bunch B. There was a huge decline in contaminations in the two gatherings. The expansion in coronary heart infections and stroke is apparent just in bunch B.

Conclusion: We found no adjustments in age at beginning, which joined with an expansion in endurance with diabetes lead to a huge expansion in age at death over the sixty years broke down.

Keywords: life span, patients, type 1 diabetes.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Umer Shehzad Ahmed,

District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital Sargodha

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is expected to reach plague proportions in this century, with a projected number of 250 million permanently diabetic patients in 2019 [1]. Whether this expansion is largely due to the scourge of type 2 diabetes, type 1 diabetes (T1DM) is also becoming more and more normal, both in Asia [2] and around the world. Despite significant progress in the treatment of diabetes in recent decades, mortality rates for patients with type 1 diabetes continue to be much higher than for those without diabetes [3]. The estimated relative risk of mortality for people with type 1 diabetes fluctuates widely, with some developers reporting values between 3 and 16. This is the main study concerning the dynamics of endurance in patients with type 1 diabetes in the Pakistan population [4]. We intend to examine the dynamics of endurance with diabetes in insulin-treated patients at the conclusion, who died between 1946 and 2005, in Lahore, Pakistan [5].

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted an investigation into the deaths recorded at the Lahore Diabetes Center between 1946 and 2005. During this period, our center was solely responsible for the administration of free medication for diabetic patients in Lahore and the surrounding area. Our review focuses on deaths of patients with type 1 diabetes, who were under 40 years of age at the onset of diabetes and stably residing in Lahore, Pakistan. The examination models were: (a) quietly registered at the Diabetes Center in Lahore; (b) insulin treatment to find; (c) died somewhere in the range of

1946 and 2005. The rejection patterns were as follows: (a) age over 40 years at onset of diabetes; (b) residence outside Lahore; (c) lack of essential data regarding treatment or duration of disease (e.g. missing clinical records). For each subject, the following information was recorded: gender, age at onset of diabetes, duration of illness, age at death, reason for death and year of death. Additional information was available for a subgroup (through accessibility of information in clinical records, not chosen by the agent - no predisposition to deliberate determination): height, weight and mean fasting blood glucose assessed. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. The weight (BMI) file was determined as follows: weight [kg]/height² [m]. Weight and stature were estimated upon enrolment at the Centre, which may not be exactly the same as the diabetes analysis with a 2-month assessment for the period 1946-2005 (more at baseline and less in current years). Mean fasting blood glucose (mean FBG) was recorded according to the qualities of the research center as recorded in the patient's records from enrollment to the end of development/disease (about 2 findings for each year). Despite the fact that it is an impotent marker of metabolic control, we chose to keep it because we now have a fixed number of expressive factors and it has an additional incentive in some examinations. The reason for death depended on successful authentication. Diabetes was considered a reason for death when no other reason was found and the patient was known to be diabetic. Unconsciousness of diabetes was recorded separately from diabetes as a reason for death.

Table 1:

	Deceased <i>n</i> = 145	Living <i>n</i> = 788	<i>P</i> *
Female (% [<i>n</i>])	44.8 (65)	50.5 (398)	0.21
Year of birth (range)	1950 (1935–1964)	1960 (1939–1979)	<0.0001
Year of type 1 diabetes diagnosis (range)	1958 (1950–1970)	1969 (1950–1980)	<0.0001
Age at onset (mean [SD] years)	8.7 (3.9)	8.2 (4.0)	0.24
Type 1 diabetes diagnosed 1965 or later (% [<i>n</i>])	11.0 (16)	66.9 (527)	<0.0001
Type 1 diabetes duration at last follow-up (mean [SD] years)†	18.7 (7.3)	34.8 (9.3)	<0.0001

**P* value for difference by vital status. †Years of type 1 diabetes duration at death or censoring at most recent follow-up for surviving participants.

Table 2:

	Pittsburgh EDC cohort			P*	ACR cohort	
	Overall n = 933	T1D diagnosed			T1D diagnosed 1965–1979 n = 1018	P†
		1950–1964 n = 390	1965–1980 n = 543			
Female (% [n])	49.6 (463)	46.2 (180)	52.1 (283)	0.07	48.7 (496)	0.20
Year of birth (range)	1953 (1935–1979)	1950 (1935–1963)	1964 (1950–1979)	<0.0001	1961 (1949–1978)	<0.0001
Year of T1D diagnosis (range)	1965 (1950–1980)	1959 (1950–1964)	1972 (1965–1980)	<0.0001	1972 (1965–1979)	0.23
Age at onset (mean [SD] years)	8.31 (3.98)	7.93 (3.87)	8.58 (4.04)	0.01	10.52 (3.98)	<0.0001
Pubertal diagnosis (% [n])	25.1 (234)	21.0 (82)	28.0 (152)	0.02	46.1 (469)	<0.0001
Deceased (% [n])	34.8 (325)	60.8 (237)	16.2 (88)	—	25.6 (261)	<0.0001
Person-years of follow-up	30,127.61	13,555.75	16,571.86	—	32,674.59	—
Mortality incidence density (95% CI)‡	1,079 (961–1,196)	1,748 (1,525–1,971)	531 (420–642)	<0.0001	799 (702–896)	0.001

T1D, type 1 diabetes. *Comparing the 1950–1964 subcohort with the 1965–1980 subcohort within Pittsburgh EDC. †Comparing the 1965–1980 Pittsburgh EDC subcohort with the 1965–1979 ACR cohort. ‡Mortality incidence density is calculated as standardized number of deaths per

Figure 1:**RESULTS:**

The survey group consisted of 849 subjects, 476 (56.8%) men and 379 (47.3%) women, enrolled in "I. Pavel", Lahore Diabetes Focus, and concerning all the previously mentioned consideration and avoidance models. The mean age at onset of diabetes was 33.37 to 9.05 years (range 2.37 to 37.99 years), with a mean term of infection at death of 21.99 to 12.63 years (range 0 to 57 years over a long period of time) and a mean age at death of 51.34 to 14.37 years (range 12 to 88 years). The main qualities of subjects with an age at determination of less than 18 years are presented in Table 1. The mean age at onset of diabetes was 13.37 4.85 years in the period 1946-1965 (no great contrasts by sex), with no critical change in the period 1966-1985 (11.81 3.48 years, no contrasts by sex) and the period 1986-2005 (11.67 4.98 years, no contrasts by sex). The mean term of infection at death was 9.57 5.35 years in the period 1946-1965 (no great gender

contrasts), followed by a steep rise ($p < 0.01$) to 17.03 8.49 years in the period 1966- 1985 (no great gender contrasts) and 28.87 12.89 years ($p < 0.001$) in the period 1986-2005 (no great gender contrasts). The mean age at death was 21.93 5.12 years in the period 1946-1965 (no critical gender contrast), followed by a considerable increase ($p < 0.002$) to 29.86 9.03 years in the period 1966-1985 (no significant gender contrast) and 41.54 14.14 years ($p < 0.002$) in the following period (no huge gender contrast). The main qualities of subjects aged 18 to 39.9 years are presented in Table 2. The mean age at onset of diabetes was 34.18 6.63 years in the period 1946-1965 (no great contrasts by sex), with no critical change in the period 1966-1985 (32.32 5.39 years, no contrasts by sexual orientation) and in the period 1986-2005 (34.47 6.34 years, no contrasts by sexual orientation). The mean duration of illness at death was 10.31 7.0 years in the period 1946-1965 (no critical contrast by sex),

followed by a critical increase ($p < 0.001$) to 23.16 12.02 years in the period 1966-1985 (no critical contrast by sex) and to 27.28 12.64 years ($p < 0.002$) in the following period (no critical contrast by sex). The mean age at death was 43.34 8.78 years in 1946-

1965 (no critical contrast by sex), followed by a considerable increase ($p < 0.002$) to 54.47 15.04 years in 1966- 1985 (no critical contrast by sex) and 59.78 13.4 years ($p < 0.002$) in 1986-2005 (no critical contrast by sex).

Table 3:

	Year of type 1 diabetes diagnosis				<i>P</i> *
	1950-1964 (<i>n</i> = 390)		1965-1980 (<i>n</i> = 543)		
	<i>n</i>	Life expectancy (95% CI)	<i>N</i>	Life expectancy (95% CI)	
Sex					
Men	210	51.5 (48.1-54.9)	260	67.0 (61.2-72.9)	<0.0001
Women	180	54.8 (50.9-58.8)	283	70.5 (65.3-76.0)	<0.0001
Age at diagnosis					
<Median age†	196	52.6 (48.9-55.9)	272	65.8 (54.7-76.9)	0.03
≥Median age	194	54.2 (50.8-57.6)	271	69.2 (65.0-73.5)	<0.0001
Prepubertal	308	54.9 (51.9-58.0)	391	70.8 (66.0-75.6)	<0.0001
Pubertal‡	82	54.0 (48.9-59.1)	152	68.5 (63.3-73.7)	<0.0001

**P* for difference in life expectancy between type 1 diabetes diagnosis year subcohorts. †Cohort-specific median age at onset: 8.1 years (interquartile range 4.8-11.3, range 0.25-15.9) in the 1950-1964 cohort and 8.8 years (interquartile range 5.9-11.8, range 0.28-16.3) in 1965-80 cohort. ‡Pubertal onset of type 1 diabetes was defined as diagnosis age ≥11 years for female and ≥12 years for male participants.

Table 4:

Age (years)	EDC diabetes diagnosed 1950-1964 (<i>n</i> = 390)		EDC diabetes diagnosed 1965-1980 (<i>n</i> = 543)		<i>P</i> *	ACR 1965-1979 (<i>n</i> = 1,018)		<i>P</i> †
	Probability of death before next age (Observed)	Estimated life expectancy (95% CI)	Probability of death before next age (Observed)	Estimated life expectancy (95% CI)		Probability of death before next age (Observed)	Estimated life expectancy (95% CI)	
Birth	0.003	53.4 (50.8-56.0)	0.000	68.8 (64.7-72.8)	<0.0001	0.000	67.2 (65.2-69.1)	0.49
1	0.008	52.6 (50.0-55.2)	0.000	67.8 (63.7-71.8)	<0.0001	0.001	66.2 (64.2-68.1)	0.49
5	0.013	49.0 (46.4-51.5)	0.000	63.8 (59.7-67.8)	<0.0001	0.003	62.2 (60.3-64.2)	0.51
10	0.011	44.6 (42.0-47.1)	0.002	58.8 (54.7-62.8)	<0.0001	0.007	57.4 (55.4-59.4)	0.56
15	0.019	40.0 (37.5-42.6)	0.000	53.9 (49.8-57.9)	<0.0001	0.005	52.8 (50.8-54.7)	0.64
20	0.049	35.7 (33.2-38.3)	0.011	48.9 (44.8-52.9)	<0.0001	0.011	48.0 (46.1-50.0)	0.72
25	0.114	32.4 (29.9-33.7)	0.039	44.4 (40.3-48.5)	<0.0001	0.031	43.5 (41.6-45.5)	0.71
30	0.151	31.3 (28.7-33.8)	0.044	41.1 (36.9-45.2)	<0.0001	0.582	39.8 (37.9-41.8)	0.60
35	0.077	31.4 (28.8-34.0)	0.059	37.9 (33.6-42.1)	0.01	0.081	37.1 (35.2-39.1)	0.77
40	0.132	28.8 (26.3-31.4)	0.052	35.1 (30.6-39.5)	0.02	0.096	35.2 (33.2-37.2)	0.97
45	0.133	27.8 (25.3-30.3)	0.073	31.9 (27.3-36.4)	0.13	0.072	31.6 (31.6-35.7)	0.48
50	0.185	26.7 (24.3-29.1)	0.179	29.2 (24.6-33.8)	0.35	0.101	31.1 (29.2-33.1)	0.45

The life expectancies presented are at the beginning of each age interval, the start of which is denoted in the age column. The final age interval is 50-85 years. **P* for difference in life expectancy between the EDC 1950-1964 and 1965-1980 subcohorts. †*P* for difference in life expectancy between EDC 1965-1980 subcohort and the ACR cohort.

DISCUSSION:

We performed a review focusing on 849 subjects, 475 (56.7%) men and 378 (45.2%) women, enrolled in "I. Pavel", the diabetes center in Lahore, with an average age of diabetes starting below 42 years and expiring between 1946 and 2005. The mean age at onset of diabetes was 31.37 to 9.06 years (range 3.37 to 37.99 years), with a normal duration of illness at death of 20.98 to 11.62 years (range 0 to 57 years) and a mean age at death of 53.37 to 15.38 years (range 13 to 89 years) [6]. One of the qualities of our test subjects is the generally high age at onset, around 30 years of age.

As we know, Pakistan is part of a region where the recurrence of diabetes is reduced in children and young people. Most of our patients with type 1 diabetes have their disease from the third or fourth decade of their life, which keeps the average age high at the beginning, around 30 years [7]. The mean age at onset of diabetes was moderately stable during the examination. Mortality in these subjects is reflected by the mean term diabetes at death and the mean age at death. Both subjects had risen over time, with a generally stable pattern in collection with age at conclusion <19 years for a long period and, to some

extent, diverse in collection with age at determination 19 years, demonstrating a precarious initial expansion of endurance, followed by a slower but at the same time certain expansion in the later period [8]. This example is confirmed by Cox's relapse test (Table 4). The average expansion of endurance with diabetes was 18.4 years for the cluster with age at baseline of less than 19 years and 16.8 years for the cluster with age at baseline of 19-38.97 years (1946-1965 versus 1986-2005). In addition, we examined the dynamics of BMI (no progression over time) and PFM (marginal essentiality for a decrease as expected), in any case, only in the group with age at determination 17-3 years [9]. The mean BMI remains stable within the usual high range, most likely due to the unintentional incorporation of a modest number of subjects with type 2 diabetes treated with insulin since their known onset who were overweight or corpulent. In addition, BMI was positively related to age at the time of disappearance, not because of a relationship with diabetes endurance, but because of its relationship with age at the time of discovery [10].

CONCLUSION:

Our review is the first to explore significant changes in mortality in young patients with T1DM in Lahore, Pakistan. It covers an extremely long period of time (sixty years), with many adjustments in the transmission of diabetes care in Pakistan and worldwide. The study of mortality should be one of the main concerns of diabetes research, as it is probably the best assessment of the nature of diabetes care.

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